

A scalable flow device for the removal of organic and inorganic pollutants from water

Graphical abstract

Highlights

- Pollutant removal by polyoxometalate ionic liquids on nanostructured Cu foam
- Custom design of a flow device for continuous water purification
- Removal of multiple organic and inorganic pollutants under flow
- Scalability and reusability from the materials to the device level

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In brief

Scalable water purification devices are a key infrastructure for humanity. This study reports the design of scalable and reusable water filtration devices where a composite filter material based on polyoxometalate ionic liquids (POM-ILs) is deposited on nanostructured copper foam (nCF). The composite filters are integrated in a flow device, which enables continuous removal of organic and inorganic pollutants from water. Pollutant-removal performance can be monitored during operation using a device-integrated UV-vis spectrometer. Scalability and reusability of the device is reported.

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Article

A scalable flow device for the removal of organic and inorganic pollutants from water

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THE BIGGER PICTURE Providing clean water is a key necessity, particularly in remote regions or after environmental or industrial emergencies. Ideally, this is achieved using scalable devices that can easily be operated by non-experts without the need for major infrastructure. In this study, a continuous water purification device is reported on, and it is operated by flowing polluted water through a series of composite filter membranes. The filters are based on polyoxometalate ionic liquids (POM-ILs) deposited on nanostructured copper foam (nCF) and have been developed to enable the removal of organic and inorganic pollutants, including toxic heavy metals or (bio)toxins. An integrated UV-vis detection system enables the real-time analysis of pollutant levels in the sample, and an open-source 3D-printed device design gives access to systems for facile production, adaptation, and scalable deployment.

SUMMARY

We report a scalable route for the removal of organic and inorganic model pollutants from water based on a nanostructured macroporous composite integrated in a custom-built flow reactor. The composite filtration material is based on a high-surface-area nanostructured Cu foam (nCF) modified with polyoxometalate ionic liquids (POM-ILs). The resulting POM-IL@nCF composite shows outstanding and scalable water-purification performance with a maximum tested volume of 900 mL. Organic pollutant removal under flow is possible with efficiencies >90%, and the filtration setup can be reused multiple times. Mixtures of organic pollutants can also be removed, and device operation was monitored through the use of *in situ* UV-visible (UV-vis) spectroscopy. Proof-of-principle studies showed that the filtration material can remove individual or mixed heavy metals from water under flow. These results provide scalable systems for decentralized water purification without major infrastructure requirements.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced water-purification technologies enable robust and efficient decontamination of wastewater in large volumes and with high efficiency.¹ This is crucial to address the global fresh-water scarcity, especially in developing countries, where drinking water is still frequently contaminated with organic and inorganic pollutants.^{2–4} In addition, promising water-purification systems usually require robust setups that can be transported

and operated without the need for major infrastructure, which is important for decentralized deployment. Also, these systems must be capable of efficient removal of microbes and organic (e.g., dyes, pharmaceuticals) and inorganic (e.g., heavy metals) pollutants from water. Much progress has been made in the design of systems that use chemical coagulation, adsorption, chelation, and filtration as purification technologies.^{1,5} Typically, traditional filter systems are comprised of porous solid-state adsorbents including clay minerals,^{6,7} zeolites,⁸ or

activated carbon.^{9,10} Nevertheless, these aforementioned adsorbents are usually targeting one specific pollutant type such that the removal of multiple pollutants in one system inevitably requires complicated combinations of different singular adsorbents. Additionally, another technical limitation for processing water volumes in traditional filtration systems is that they are limited by low flow rates.¹¹

To this end, tremendous efforts have been made to explore composite materials with tunable compositions and structures to access systems where multiple contaminants can be removed by one type of material.^{12–14} For example, Hu and co-workers¹⁵ developed Zr-based metal-organic frameworks featuring high adsorption capacity and fast adsorption kinetics for both organic dyes (methylene blue, methyl orange) and heavy metals (Pb²⁺, Cr³⁺, and Cu²⁺), and Chen et al.¹⁶ fabricated sodium polyacrylate intercalated layered double hydroxide composites, demonstrating the efficient removal of methylene blue dye, Pb²⁺, and Hg²⁺ ions in aqueous medium. In another example by Sankar et al.,¹⁷ Ag or MnO₂ nanoparticles were embedded into nanocrystalline AlOOH-chitosan granular composite materials, where decontamination targets can be customized for bacterial (*E. coli*) or heavy-metal (Pb²⁺) removal.

Apart from the composite materials above, ionic liquids (ILs), a family of tunable functional substances,^{18,19} have also been utilized to modify many other materials, where versatile composites for water decontamination were successfully designed. This involves bacterial (*E. coli*) removal by IL-grafted polyamide 6²⁰ and organic dye (methylene blue, methyl orange) removal by IL-impregnated metal-organic frameworks.²¹ Also, Li and co-workers²² developed IL-grafted polyethersulfone nanofibrous membranes, which exhibited high adsorption capacity for both a heavy-metal ion (Cd²⁺) and an organic dye (Congo red) as well as good antibacterial activity (toward *E. coli* and *S. aureus*).

Recently, some of the authors have developed polyoxometalate (POM)-based supported IL phases (POM-SILPs), which showed promising potential for the efficient removal of a variety of pollutants from wastewater.^{23,24} The first POM-SILP was prepared by immobilizing POM-ILs on the surface of porous SiO₂ particles, leading to a POM-IL@SiO₂ composite. The POM-IL employed consists of lacunary Keggin-type tungstate anions featuring heavy-metal-binding sites, and long-chain quaternary organo-ammonium cations with antimicrobial activity, leading to water-insoluble but hydrophilic materials.^{25–28} Based on their unique properties, POM-SILPs displayed a high decontamination capability for a series of contaminants including toxic heavy metals, radionuclides, organic dyes, and even microbes. The POM-SILPs (POM-IL@SiO₂) were deployed as filtration components in small filter columns with a relatively low flow rate of ca. 6 mL min⁻¹,^{23,25} and so purification of larger water volumes has thus far not been demonstrated. One approach to overcome this issue was the design of POM-SILPs based on magnetic core-shell Fe₂O₃@SiO₂ particles. These composites (POM-IL@Fe₂O₃@SiO₂) could be dispersed in the polluted water and simply removed using a permanent magnet.²⁴ To date, integration of these systems into a continuous purification system for upscaling has not been reported. In this regard, flow-through filtration setups are attracting global interest, as they can offer enormous scaling potential for efficient pollutant removal from water due to

the enhanced mass transport, increased ratio of filter material area to reactor volume, and increased interaction interfaces between filter material and polluted water.^{29,30}

In order to integrate POM-SILPs into a continuous flow filtration setup, deposition of POM-ILs on porous supports with a large surface area is required. Here, we highlight that the use of macroporous metal foams is a promising route to this end. Metal foams, such as Cu foam (**CF**), feature high and adjustable porosity, mechanical robustness, and tunable surface morphology and have been used in a wide range of technologies,^{31,32} including electrocatalytic water splitting,^{33,34} fuel cells,³⁵ and supercapacitors³⁶ as well as rechargeable battery electrodes.³⁷ To the best of our knowledge, metal foams have not been explored as monolithic porous POM-IL supports for water decontamination. Here, we present the use of nanostructured **CF (nCF)** as support for the stable deposition of POM-ILs using a facile, scalable fabrication route,³⁸ resulting in the new composite **POM-IL@nCF**. As expected, the nanostructured morphology of the **nCF** support facilitates higher POM-IL loadings compared with the unmodified **CF** reference. In the next step, the monolithic composite was integrated into a custom-built flow reactor (see Figure 1), which enabled scalable water purification for increased volume flows up to 900 mL (150 mL × 6 runs).^{29,39–41} Comparison with the literature shows that the present device combines filtration scalability and robustness for single- and mixed-pollutant removal, benefitting from efficient mass transfer from the wastewater to the **POM-IL@nCF** sorbent layer under flow (see Table S1). In addition, the device shows a unique stimuli response where an increase of the pollutant-removal rate is observed during operation. Mechanistic studies using *in situ* UV-visible (UV-vis) spectroscopy provide us with initial insights into the basis of this unique observation (see Figure 1).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

POM-IL@nCF composite material fabrication and characterization

In this work, we propose a scalable design approach, where POM-ILs are stably immobilized on **nCF**, leading to porous composite monoliths for the continuous removal of organic and inorganic pollutants from water by integration in a flow reactor.

The POM-ILs were synthesized and purified according to an established cation metathesis route,^{23,24,28,42} which combines lacunary-Keggin cluster anions ([α -SiW₁₁O₃₉]⁸⁻)⁴³ and tetra-*n*-heptyl ammonium cations (Q⁷⁺ = (n-C₇H₁₅)₄N⁺)⁴⁴ to give the POM-IL, namely (Q⁷⁺)₈[α -SiW₁₁O₃₉] (see Figure 1A). The as-prepared POM-IL is highly viscous and shows high solubility in a wide range of organic solvents (e.g., acetone).⁴⁵ The hydrophilicity of the POM-ILs was evaluated by the sessile drop method, giving a contact angle of 66.2° on a flat glass surface (see Figure S1); for synthetic and analytical details, see the supplemental information and experimental procedures. The bulk nanostructuring of pure **CF** (2 × 10 × 20 mm) was performed based on a literature route where **CF** is immersed in an aqueous sodium hydroxide solution containing ammonium peroxosulfate as an oxidizing agent. This leads to the formation of blue Cu(OH)₂ nanowires (length: ca. 14 μm, diameter: ca. 5 nm) and black

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the scope of research on water decontamination by POM-IL@nCF under flow

(A) Structures of the POM-IL anion and cation components.

(B) Fabrication process of nanostructured Cu foam (nCF) and the composite material POM-IL@nCF.

(C and D) Integration of the POM-IL@nCF monolithic composite into a custom-built continuous flow reactor for the removal of Patent Blue V (PBV) model pollutant, and (D) monitored removal process by *in situ* UV-vis spectroscopy.

CuO “nanoflowers” (diameter: ca. 3.5 μm) on the two faces of the CF (see Figures 2 and S2 and the experimental procedures).³⁸ Due to the nanostructured surfaces, the Brunauer, Emmett, and Teller (BET) specific surface area of nCF showed a considerable increase compared with the pure CF (see Table S2). For POM-IL immobilization, nCF was immersed in a POM-IL stock solution ($V_{\text{acetone}} = 10 \text{ mL}$, $m_{\text{POM-IL}} = 2 \text{ g}$) for 24 h in a sealed setup (see Figure S3). Subsequent drying of the composite under vacuum gave the POM-IL@nCF composite (see Figure 1B). To assess the importance of CF nanostructuring, the above immersion procedure was also conducted on the unmodified CF, which led to POM-IL@CF. POM-IL@CF, nCF, and CF were used as references throughout this study.

Gravimetric studies of the samples showed a higher POM-IL loading for POM-IL@nCF (71.3 wt %), while a lower value was observed for POM-IL@CF (63.8 wt %), highlighting the influence of CF nanostructuring for POM-IL deposition. Nitrogen sorption analyses of both composites showed decreased BET specific surface area and pore volume compared with the respective non-POM-IL-containing supports, indicative of the successful POM-IL anchoring onto the external and internal surfaces of the supports (see supplemental information and Table S2). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) further supports a successful coating of POM-IL (thickness: ca. 1.5 μm) on the surface of nCF (see Figures 3A and S4), where the integrity of the nanostructures is visible in the “cracked” region. In contrast, a thinner POM-IL layer (thickness: ca. 0.5 μm) was observed on non-nCF based on the SEM data (see Figure S5). Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) elemental mapping (see Figures 3B–3D and S6) shows a homogeneous distribution of the elements C, Cu, W, and O on the composite surface. Attenuated total reflection Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy (see Fig-

ure 3E) indicated the presence and structural integrity of the POM anion and the IL cation (for detailed assignments of the characteristic signals, see the experimental procedures). Further, hydrophilicity analysis of the POM-IL@nCF composite by the sessile drop method (using aqueous Patent Blue V [PBV] solution as medium, [PBV] = 16 μM) gave a contact angle of 73.2°, presenting a more hydrophilic surface than that of POM-IL@CF (97.1°). Notably, due to the presence of surface hydroxyl groups (vibrational modes at 3,562 and 3,292 cm^{-1} ; see Figure 3E and the experimental procedures), the nCF support is highly wettable, so the sessile drop immediately permeated the nanostructured surface. In comparison, a significantly lower wettability and higher contact angle is observed for unmodified CF (127.1°; see Figure S7), indicating nCF as a more competitive support material applied for advanced water purification.

Integration of POM-IL@nCF into a flow reactor for efficient water purification

The performance of POM-IL@nCF and references for water purification was assessed in a 3D-printed flow-through reactor setup containing four samples (dimensions: 2 \times 10 \times 20 mm each) of the investigated composite positioned on a customized holder. Connection of the reactor inlet and outlet to a 3D-printed reservoir allowed cycling of the reaction solution through the porous composites at flow rates ranging from 43.9 to 205.8 mL min^{-1} (see Figures 1C, S8, and S9). Organic pollutant model (anionic PBV, cationic Rhodamine B [RhB]) removal was monitored by installation of a custom-made flow-through cell for *in situ* UV-vis analysis downstream to the reactor. Samples for heavy-metal removal (1 mL each) were collected at the chosen time intervals for analysis by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES). Before water-purification

Figure 2. Nanostructuring of CF

(A–C) Photograph (A) and SEM images (B and C) of CF.

(D–F) Photograph (D) and SEM images (E and F) of the blue $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ face of the nCF.

(G–I) Photograph (G) and SEM images (H and I) of the black CuO face of the nCF.

experiments, a blank run was performed using deionized water only (flow rate = $125.7 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$). A measurable but very low leaching of the POM-IL ($<0.7 \text{ wt } \%$) into the aqueous phase was identified by ICP-OES under 120 min continuous operation, and further leaching was not observed after prolonged flow-through periods (180 and 210 min).

Removal of organic model pollutants

PBV dye, a water-soluble organic triphenyl methane (trityl) derivative,⁴⁶ was chosen as a model aromatic organic pollutant. Batches of aqueous PBV solutions ($[\text{PBV}] = 16 \mu\text{M}$, $V = 150 \text{ mL}$) were prepared and used for purification tests. As a preliminary test, a static dye removal experiment was performed where four POM-IL@nCF filters ($2 \times 10 \times 20 \text{ mm}$) were immersed in PBV solution (150 mL) without flow or stirring. After 120 min, only 8.3% dye removal was observed (see Figure S10).

For filtration under flow, PBV solutions were continuously pumped through the POM-IL@nCF filtration setup for 120 min. The changes of absorbance of the PBV solution were monitored by *in situ* UV-vis spectroscopy. First, the influence of flow rate on the PBV-removal performance was investigated. To this end, three flow rates were studied (in triplicate), that is, 43.9, 125.7, and $205.8 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$. The resulting UV-vis spectral changes over time are shown in the supplemental information (see Figure S11), from which the percentage removal trends of PBV under different flow rates are compared (see Figure 4A). The lowest performance, namely the lowest removal percentage (87.4%), was observed for the flow rate of 43.9 mL min^{-1} (slowest removal kinetics). Due to the limited flow rate, the sorption equilibrium of PBV cannot be reached before 120 min. This is attributed to slow diffusional mass transport in the stagnant film around the filter. In

contrast, flow rates of 125.7 and $205.8 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$ showed similar removal trends: sorption equilibria were reached at ca. 80 min, and comparable removal percentages of 92.9% and 95.5%, respectively, were observed. The increased convection likely reduced the thickness of the stagnant film. By this, mass-transport limitations were reduced, and finally, the removal of the pollutant was accelerated. Thus, a flow rate of $125.7 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$ is sufficient to ensure mass transport within the porous POM-IL@CF composite, so the subsequent flow experiments were performed at $125.7 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$.

In terms of reference samples, POM-IL@CF, with lower POM-IL loading, presented also lower removal percentage (87.1%) over the 120 min one, while the

unmodified CF showed almost negligible performance (2%; see Figures 4B, S12A, and S12B). Interestingly, nCF showed an adsorption equilibrium at ca. 10 min with 10.8% removal percentage (see Figures 4B and S12C). We propose that this considerable removal percentage by nCF was due to the effect of nanostructuring, resulting in (most likely electrostatic) physisorption of the dye on the Cu oxide/hydroxide surface. Additional contributing factors are the high wettability and high specific surface area (see Figure S7B and Table S2). In addition, hydroxyl surface groups (see Figure 3E and the experimental procedures) are known for their pollutant-binding properties.^{47,48}

Next, the reusability of the POM-IL@nCF filtration setup was examined in six consecutive runs (720 min in total) of PBV-removal tests at the flow rate of $125.7 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$ (see Figures 4C and S13). After each run, the purified simulated wastewater was completely withdrawn from the setup, which was then refilled with fresh PBV solution ($[\text{PBV}] = 16 \mu\text{M}$, $\text{pH} = 6.3$) without replacing the POM-IL@nCF composite filter. Over the course of the six runs, the performance of the setup remained essentially stable for four runs, while, subsequently, a drop in performance was noted. The PBV-removal trends for the six runs are displayed (see Figure 4C), and the slopes of the corresponding linear ranges in each run have been fitted to illustrate the removal rates (see Figure S14). In detail, run 1 demonstrated a considerable increase in PBV-removal rates, with a notable change of slope at 52 min. As shown, the PBV-removal rate was doubled (from 0.9% to $1.9\% \text{ min}^{-1}$) after 52 min in run 1, indicating a unique stimuli response that results in increased dye-removal kinetics. This is further supported by run 2, which gave a further increased removal rate ($2.0\% \text{ min}^{-1}$) and comparable removal

Figure 3. Characterization of the composites

(A–D) SEM image of the **POM-IL@nCF** surface (A) and corresponding SEM-EDX mapping (B–D).

(E) ATR-FTIR spectra of **CF**, **nCF**, **POM**, **POM-IL**, and **POM-IL@nCF**.

percentage (90.50%). The increasing removal kinetics observed during runs 1 and 2 might be due to structural changes of the POM-IL surface coating under flow, which might modulate the IL-liquid interfacial interactions.^{49,50} Previous studies have indeed reported structure changes of ILs at surfaces when a shearing force was applied.^{51,52}

Runs 3 and 4 underwent minor performance loss (removal percentages: 87.3% and 85.4%, respectively) and a drop in removal rates (1.3% and 1.2% min⁻¹), indicating reasonably stable performance of the **POM-IL@nCF** composite over 4 runs (600 mL PBV solution). In runs 5 (removal percentage: 63.7%, removal rate: 0.5% min⁻¹) and 6 (removal percentage: 52.8%, removal rate: 0.4% min⁻¹), significant performance drops were noted. This indicates that a saturation in PBV uptake by **POM-IL@nCF** was reached. For a performance comparison with previous works on POM-ILs, see details in Table S3. Note that, compared with the related POM-SILP filtration composites (POM-IL@SiO₂ and POM-IL@Fe₂O₃@SiO₂),^{23,24} the **POM-IL@nCF** composite exhibited significantly higher PBV-removal performance even though the POM-IL loading was only 3.5 times higher. Even after 6 consecutive runs, the dye uptake of **POM-IL@nCF** still exceeded 1,200 nmol, while those of fresh POM-IL@SiO₂ and POM-IL@Fe₂O₃@SiO₂ were 304 and 158 nmol, respectively.

Notably, the reuse of **nCF** support material was also achievable by rinsing the **POM-IL@nCF** composite material with acetone after PBV-removal tests. According to the powder XRD (pXRD) pattern (see Figure S15), the structures of the **nCF** are fully retained, indicating great sustainability of the support material for scalable water purification under flow.

To gain mechanistic insights into the performance of **POM-IL@nCF** for PBV removal, post-filtration analyses were carried out. ATR-FTIR spectroscopy of **POM-IL@nCF** shows the increase of the characteristic PBV vibrational modes (at 1,582, 1,343, 1,188, and 1,153 cm⁻¹) when comparing samples after runs 1, 4, and 6, highlighting the sustaining uptake of PBV by the **POM-IL@nCF** composite (see Figure 4D). Also, the disappearance of hydroxyl groups (vibrational modes at 3,562 and 3,292), originating from the **nCF** support (see Figure 3E), was observed after consecutive runs of PBV-removal tests (see Figure 4D). This provides evidence on the accumulation of adsorbed PBV dye on the surface of the **POM-IL@nCF** composite. In addition, compared with fresh **POM-IL@nCF** (water contact angle, 73.2°), hydrophilicity evaluation of the post-filtration **POM-IL@nCF** surface displayed gradually increasing water contact angles (92.9° for 52 min and 128.1° for 120 min) over the course of run 1, while, compared with that, a slightly decreased value (116.0°) was observed after run 4. Notably, after run 6, a significant increase in surface hydrophilicity (water contact angle, 71.5°) was observed (see Figure S16). These results suggest a changing surface hydrophilicity of **POM-IL@nCF** during operation that thereby leads to varying removal rates over the 6 runs of PBV-removal tests (see Figure S14). Furthermore, changing surface morphologies were found after dye removal compared with fresh **POM-IL@nCF** (see Figures S4 and S17), which could be the reason for the observed varying PBV-removal rates.

Next, we explored the effect of pH change for organic dye removal by **POM-IL@nCF**. Thus, PBV solution ([PBV] = 16 μM, native pH = 6.3) was acidified to pH 3.6 (aqueous HCl, 4 M), and dye removal was tested under flow as described above. After 120 min, a removal percentage of 88.9% was observed (see Figure S18), which was lower by 4% compared with the PBV-removal test at pH 6.3 (92.9%). This result highlights the robustness of the composite material for efficient PBV removal even at low pH values.

To explore the behavior with a cationic dye, we performed filtration studies with RhB ([RhB] = 16 μM), a xanthene dye with high toxicity.⁵³ Under identical experimental conditions, lower performance for RhB removal was observed for the **POM-IL@nCF** composite compared with the removal tests for the anionic PBV dye (see Figures 4A and 4B), and removal percentages of 40.4% and 58.6% at 120 and 600 min, respectively, are reported (see Figure S19). To explore the underlying reason for the uptake difference, anionic PBV and cationic RhB were mixed for a comparative removal test. The **POM-IL@nCF** composite material still displayed outstanding PBV-removal performance (93.2% under mixture condition, 92.9% for pure PBV), while the removal percentage of RhB dropped to 25.9% in the mixture (see Figure S20). This indicates competitive uptake with preferential binding of the anionic PBV over the cationic RhB by **POM-IL@nCF**. Mechanistic studies are underway to explore these differences by experiment and theory.

Figure 4. PBV-removal performance by **POM-IL@nCF** composite and references ([PBV] = 16 μ M)

(A) Comparison of the PBV-removal trends of **POM-IL@nCF** at different flow rates.

(B) Comparison of PBV-removal trend of **POM-IL@nCF** and references at flow rate of 125.7 mL min^{-1} ; inset: time-dependent UV-vis spectra collected for **POM-IL@nCF**.

(C) Reusability test of **POM-IL@nCF** composite.

(D) ATR-FTIR spectra of **POM-IL@nCF** composite before and after PBV-removal tests.

Removal of heavy metals

The performance of the **POM-IL@nCF** composite for heavy-metal removal from water was also explored. Typical heavy-metal-ion pollutant models MnO_4^- , Ni^{2+} , and Co^{2+} were subjected to an identical flow reactor setup. To simulate high contamination and test removal efficiency, the metal-ion concentrations are raised up to 45,000 times above the World Health Organization (WHO) guideline levels for drinking water (see Table 1).⁵⁴ ICP-OES analyses of the respective single-ion solutions after flow purification (210 min) revealed a very high MnO_4^- uptake capacity (97.6%) of the **POM-IL@nCF** composite, while relatively low performances for Ni^{2+} (63.3%) and Co^{2+} (38.3%) were observed (see Figure 5A). Correspondingly, the **nCF** demonstrated significantly lower metal removal in the range of approximately 3%–8% (see Table 1, entries 1–3, and Figure 5A).

Next, two or three heavy-metal ions were mixed in water to understand the affinity of heavy-metal ions to the adsorption sites

of **POM-IL@nCF** (see Figure 5B). For the two-metal cation case (Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , 1.3 mM each), the overall removal percentage of both Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} (see Table 1, entry 4) was significantly lower compared with the corresponding single-metal-removal tests (see Table 1, entries 2–3), suggesting competitive binding for Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} by the vacant metal-binding site of $[\alpha\text{-SiW}_{11}\text{O}_{39}]^{9-}$ in the POM-IL. Interestingly, when MnO_4^- is mixed with Ni^{2+} or Co^{2+} , quantitative removal of MnO_4^- can be achieved, while the mixed cation demonstrated low removal percentages in the 2%–3% range (see Table 1, entries 5–6). This result reveals the preferable affinity of **POM-IL@nCF** to MnO_4^- , which is consistent with the competitive removal test in the three-metal experiments using MnO_4^- , Ni^{2+} , and Co^{2+} in one batch (see Table 1, entry 7).

The excellent MnO_4^- -anion-removal performance of **POM-IL@nCF** in terms of both single- and mixed-metal-ion solutions indicated that the heavy-metal-removal activity by **POM-IL@nCF**

Table 1. Heavy-metal-removal performance of POM-IL@nCF and nCF

Entry	Heavy metal (conc.) [WHO guideline level]	Heavy-metal removal ^a by POM-IL@nCF [nCF], %	Heavy-metal concentration (mM) after filtration by POM-IL@nCF [nCF]
1	MnO ₄ ⁻ (1.15 mM) [0.05 μM]	97.6 [7.9]	0.028 [1.06]
2	Ni ²⁺ (1.3 mM) [0.34 μM]	63.3 [3.3]	0.48 [1.26]
3	Co ²⁺ (1.3 mM) [-]	38.0 [3.4]	0.81 [1.26]
4	Ni ²⁺	14.9	1.11
	Co ²⁺	13.3	1.13
5	MnO ₄ ⁻	100.0	0.0
	Ni ²⁺	2.2	1.27
6	MnO ₄ ⁻	98.6	0.02
	Co ²⁺	3.0	1.26
7	MnO ₄ ⁻	100.0	0.0
	Ni ²⁺	11.8	1.15
	Co ²⁺	2.0	1.27
8	Cr ₂ O ₇ ²⁻ (1.2 mM) [0.96 μM]	97.5 [-]	0.03

^aV_{heavy metal solution} = 150 mL, \dot{V} = 125.7 mL min⁻¹, t_{operation} = 210 min.

was mechanistically driven by both lacunary sorption and electrostatic interaction with the tetra-*n*-heptyl ammonium cation (Q⁷ = (n-C₇H₁₅)₄N⁺) of the POM-IL. To further prove this proposed mechanism, a parallel test was performed to remove another model anion (Cr₂O₇²⁻) from water by **POM-IL@nCF** based on the standard procedure described above. As shown, after 210 min flow time, the removal percentages of Cr₂O₇²⁻ and MnO₄⁻ by **POM-IL@nCF** are almost identical (97.5% and 97.6%, respectively; see Figure 5C). Also, they follow a similar removal trend, although faster binding kinetics are observed for dichromate compared with permanganate (see Table 1, entry 8).

In addition, the remaining concentrations of the chosen heavy-metal ions after removal tests by **POM-IL@nCF** are presented (see Table 1), most of which are higher than the WHO levels because of the intensively raised initial concentration. Notably, the superior MnO₄⁻ uptake capacity of the **POM-IL@nCF** composite is still observed for mixed-heavy-metal-removal test exiting of Ni²⁺ (see Table 1, entries 5 and 7).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we report the first example of immobilizing POM-IL on a monolithic nCF support. The resulting **POM-IL@nCF** composite materials are integrated into a custom-built flow reactor, opening a new avenue for applicable efficient water purification under varying flow rates at a relatively large volume and long-term scale. High removal efficiency of PBV is reported together with insights into the removal kinetics from **POM-IL@nCF**, and the removal performance of the composite is proved to be stable through reusability tests. Excellent potential in efficient heavy-metal removal of **POM-IL@nCF** is also witnessed, ranging from single-metal to mixed-metal conditions (MnO₄⁻, Cr₂O₇²⁻, Ni²⁺, and Co²⁺), with relative preference over metal-anion uptake. As a prototype development, we propose that this new composite materials design concept and flowing system integration technology will enable the targeted development of simultaneous removal of multiple contaminant mixtures (inorganics and organics) under real conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Resource availability

Lead contact

Further information and requests for resources and reagents should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contact, Dr. Dandan Gao (dandan.gao@uni-mainz.de).

Materials availability

There are restrictions to the availability of **POM-IL@nCF** because of the lack of an external centralized repository for its distribution and our need to maintain the stock. We are glad to share **POM-IL@nCF** with reasonable compensation by requestor for its processing and shipping.

Data and code availability

All data shown in this manuscript (including files for the 3D-printed reactor parts) have been deposited at zenodo.org under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7967561> and are publicly available as of the date of publication. Any additional information required to reanalyze the data reported in this paper is available from the [lead contact](#) upon request.

Synthesis of K₈[α-SiW₁₁O₃₉]·13H₂O (POM)

The compound was synthesized according to the published procedure.^{34,45} Na₂WO₄·2H₂O (76 g) is dissolved in 300 mL distilled water in a 500 mL beaker, and the solution is heated to 100°C. 4 M aqueous HCl (64 mL) is added dropwise to the boiling solution at vigorous stirring in the following 20–30 min. Any precipitate (tungstic acid) formed is allowed to redissolve before adding any further HCl acid. Then, sodium metasilicate pentahydrate solution (Na₂·SiO₃·5H₂O, 4.6 g in 60 mL water) is added. The pH of the mixed solution is adjusted to 5.5 by quick addition of aqueous HCl (4 M, 40–50 mL). Next, the mixed solution is boiled for 1 h and removed from the heating plate. After cooling to room temperature, solid KCl powder (100 g) is added, and a white precipitate is formed. The solid product is collected by filtration and washed with two 50 mL portions of aqueous cold KCl solution (1 M) followed by 100 mL portions of cold water. The crude product is recrystallized from hot water and filtered, and the colorless crystalline product is dried in the desiccator under vacuum. Purity was confirmed by ATR-IR (characteristic bands are given as wavenumbers using the following abbreviations: s, strong; m, medium; w, weak): 3,392 (s), 2,335 (w), 1,620 (s), 980 (m), 946 (s), 858 (s), 777 (s), 704 (s), 495 (m), and 448 cm⁻¹ (m).

Synthesis of (Q⁷)₈[α-SiW₁₁O₃₉] (POM-IL)

The as-prepared K₈[α-SiW₁₁O₃₉]·13H₂O (5 g, 1 equiv) was dissolved in 50 mL water and heated to 50°C for a better solubility, and a solution of the desired

Figure 5. Heavy-metal-removal performance under flow

(A–D) Single-metal removal by **POM-IL@nCF** and **nCF** (A), mixed-metal removal by **POM-IL@nCF** (B), comparably efficient removal of single-metal anions by **POM-IL@nCF** (C), and corresponding removal trend tracking (D).

tetra-*n*-heptyl ammonium bromide salt (6.092 g, 8 equiv) in toluene (100 mL) was added. The mixture was vigorously stirred for 30 min, and the organic layer was separated, which was then extracted with water (50 mL) 6 times. After removal of the solvent at reduced pressure, the light yellow, highly viscous liquid was thoroughly washed once with 50 mL toluene and three times with 50 mL chloroform. ATR-FTIR for POM-IL (characteristic bands are given as wavenumbers using the same abbreviations as above): 2,953/2,914/2,845 (s), 1,631 (w), 1,462 (s), 1,369 (m), 1,145 (w), 1,068 (w), 991 (m), 930 (m), 890 (s), 783 (s), 713 (m), 682 (m), 511 (w), and 4,681 cm⁻¹ (w).

Nanostructuring of CF

Nanostructuring of **CF** was performed using a modification of our previously reported route.³⁸ In brief, the prepared cleaned **CF** was immersed into 15 mL oxidizing aqueous solution (0.133 M ammonium peroxosulfate, 2.66 M NaOH) at room temperature for 40 min, from which an **nCF** was obtained, featuring Cu(OH)₂ nanowires and CuO nanoflowers on two faces. pXRD patterns show predominantly Cu(OH)₂ diffraction signals for the blue face, while the black face predominantly shows the corresponding CuO diffraction peaks. Note that both faces show residual signals for the other nanostructure due to the porous structure of the electrode. ATR-FTIR spectra also indicate the structure assignments (hydroxyl groups at 3,562 and 3,292 cm⁻¹, Cu-O-H bending at 933 cm⁻¹, and Cu-O stretching modes at 678 cm⁻¹).

Fabrication of POM-IL-coated nCF (POM-IL@nCF)

POM-IL@nCF was fabricated via a facile one-step immersion method at room temperature (for detailed coating steps, see Figure S3). Firstly, a homogeneous POM-IL solution was prepared by completely dissolving POM-IL (2 g) in acetone (10 mL), in which the as-prepared **nCF** (3 pieces) was immersed. Then, the setup was sealed carefully with a parafilm on the top for 24 h, followed by evaporation in air for 24 h and subsequent vacuum drying. Additionally, the identical fabrication procedure was applied for pure **CF**, resulting in a reference material, **POM-IL@CF**.

Supplemental information

Supplemental information can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.device.2023.100020>.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

E.O.O., D.G., S.R.W., D.Z., and C.S. developed the research ideas and designed the experimental methodologies. E.O.O., D.G., R.G., A.M., and R.L. performed experiments and analyzed and curated data. F.G. and D.Z. developed flow methodologies and code. D.G., S.R.W., D.Z., and C.S. acquired funding, supervised the project, and provided project administration. All authors co-wrote, reviewed, and edited the manuscript.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

INCLUSION AND DIVERSITY

We support inclusive, diverse, and equitable conduct of research.

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DEVICE, Volume 1

Supplemental information

**A scalable flow device for the removal of organic
and inorganic pollutants from water**

**Ekemena O. Oseghe, Fabian Guba, Archismita Misra, Ruihao Gong, Rongji Liu, Siegfried
R. Waldvogel, Dirk Ziegenbalg, Carsten Streb, and Dandan Gao**

1. Instrumentation and experimental methods

Powder X-ray diffraction (pXRD) patterns were recorded on a Rigaku XRD-6000 diffractometer at the following conditions: 40 kV, 40 mA, Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.154$ nm).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) analytical data were obtained using a Hitachi 5200 SEM equipped with an EDX detector.

Attenuated total reflection Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) was carried out on a Bruker Tensor 27 equipped with a PIKE Miracle Diamond ATR unit. Signals are given as wavenumbers in cm⁻¹ using the following abbreviations: s - strong, m - medium, w - weak.

Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) was conducted on an Agilent 5800 ICP-OES (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA) instrument. All measurements were conducted in aqueous HNO₃ solution.

In situ UV-Vis spectroscopy was recorded on an Avantes AvaSpec-ULS2048CL detector unit coupled with an AVA AvaLight-DH-S-BAL light source, combining with a custom-made flow reactor integrated with a cuvette (Outer diameter: 9.85 mm, inner diameter: 7.85 mm, length: 83 mm). For each run, 60 UV-Vis spectra are recorded with a time interval of 2 min between each spectrum.

Nitrogen physisorption was conducted on the Quadrasorb Surface Area and Pore Size Analyzer. Before measurement, sample degassing was performed on the FloVac Degaser from Quantachrome at 333 K (60°C) at vacuum for 22 h. N₂ was used as adsorbate. The evaluation of the pore distribution after BJH evaluation of the pore diameter was performed using the BJH Kernel including the KJS correction.

Contact angle measurements were performed using the sessile drop method using Patent blue V solution (PBV, 16 μ M, water solution). Three points were analyzed per sample surface.

Chemicals: Sodium tungstate dihydrate (VWR, CAS No. 10213-10-2), Sodium metasilicate pentahydrate (VWR, CAS No. 10213-79-3), Potassium chloride (Carl Roth, CAS No. 7447-40-7), Tetraheptylammonium bromide (Thermo Scientific, CAS No. 4368-51-8), Ammonium persulfate (Honeywell, CAS No. 7727-54-0), Sodium hydroxide (ROTH, CAS No. 1370-73-2), Patent blue V (Sigma-Aldrich, CAS No. 20262-76-4), Rhodamine B (Thermo Fisher, CAS No. 81-88-9), NiSO₄·6H₂O (Thermo Scientific, CAS No. 10101-97-0), CoCl₂·6H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich, CAS No. 7791-13-1), KMnO₄ (Alfa Aesar, CAS No. 7722-64-7), K₂Cr₂O₇ (Sigma-Aldrich, CAS No. 7778-50-9). Commercial Cu foam (**CF**, dimensions 2 mm x 10 mm x 20 mm, 90 % porosity) was purchased from Xiamen Tmax Battery Equipments Limited, China. Before using, the **CF** was cleaned with acetone, deionized water, and ethanol, respectively (immersion time: 15 min per solvent). All chemicals were used as received.

2. Comparison table

Table S1: Water treatment performance comparison between the device reported, and other state-of-the-art water purification methods.

Adsorbents	Purification methods	Target pollutants		Volume (mL)	Removal time (h)	Removal percentage (%)	Ref.
		Organic dye [concentration]	Heavy metals [concentration]				
3-Mercaptopropylsilyl-sepiolite	Batch	-	Pb ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ [0.05 to 1 mmol L ⁻¹]	10	24	Concentration-dependent	1
Na-montmorillonite	Continuous column system	-	Cd ²⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ [1 mmol L ⁻¹]	25	N.A.	pH-dependent	2
NaY zeolite	Magnetic removal process	-	Cr ³⁺ , Cu ²⁺ and Zn ²⁺ [100 - 1000 mg L ⁻¹]	30	24	Metal concentration-dependent	3
Norit ROX 0.8 activated carbon	Batch	anionic and cationic dyes [600 mg L ⁻¹]	-	50	48	Acidity of the dye-dependent	4
Fe ₃ O ₄ @SiO ₂ @UiO-66-NH ₂	Batch	Methylene Blue, Methyl Orange [20 mg L ⁻¹]	Pb ²⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , Cu ²⁺ [20 mg L ⁻¹]	10	1	97 - 100	5
PAAS/LDH	Batch	Methylene Blue [50 mg L ⁻¹]	Pb ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺ [50 mg L ⁻¹]	N.A.	1	96 – 99.6	6
MIM][PF6]/MIL-53(Al)	Batch	Methylene Blue, Methyl Orange [10 mg L ⁻¹]	-	N.A.	3	99.2%	7
PES-g-IL	Batch in a shaker	Anionic Congo Red [60 mg L ⁻¹]	Cd ²⁺ [160 mg L ⁻¹]	50	N.A.	pH and temperature-dependent	8
POM-IL@SiO ₂	Continuous column	Anionic PBV [32 μmol L ⁻¹]	Pb ²⁺ [2.2 mmol L ⁻¹] Ni ²⁺ [1.3 mmol L ⁻¹] Cu ²⁺ [1.3 mmol L ⁻¹] Cr ³⁺ [1.2 mmol L ⁻¹] Co ²⁺ [1.3 mmol L ⁻¹] UO ₂ ²⁺ [430 μmol L ⁻¹]	10	24 h	95 (PBV) 99 (Pb ²⁺) 89 (Ni ²⁺) 100 (Cu ²⁺) 78 (Cr ³⁺) 80 (Co ²⁺) 100 (UO ₂ ²⁺)	9

POM-IL@Fe ₂ O ₃ @SiO ₂	Batch / Magnetic removal	Anionic PBV [32 μmol L ⁻¹]	Pb ²⁺ [2.2 mmol L ⁻¹] Ni ²⁺ [1.3 mmol L ⁻¹] Cu ²⁺ [1.3 mmol L ⁻¹] Co ²⁺ [1.3 mmol L ⁻¹] MnO ₄ ⁻ [1.15 mmol L ⁻¹]	5	24 h	99 (PBV) 99 (Pb ²⁺) 90 (Ni ²⁺) 99 (Cu ²⁺) 75 (Co ²⁺) 99 (MnO ₄ ⁻)	10
POM-IL@nCF	Continuous Flow	Anionic PBV ^a [16 μmol L ⁻¹] Cationic Rhodamine B [16 μmol L ⁻¹]	Ni ²⁺ [1.3 mmol L ⁻¹] ^b Co ²⁺ [1.3 mmol L ⁻¹] MnO ₄ ⁻ [1.3 mmol L ⁻¹] Cr ₂ O ₇ ²⁻ [1.3 mmol L ⁻¹]	150 (6 runs, 900 mL in total)	2 h (12 h)	92.9 (PBV) 40.4 (Rh B) 63.3 (Ni²⁺) 38.0 (Co²⁺) 97.6 (MnO₄⁻) 97.5 (Cr₂O₇²⁻)	This work

Supplemental explanation related to Table S1

^a: simultaneous removal of PBV and RhB was possible, see main manuscript for details

^b: simultaneous removal of metal cations and anions was possible, see main manuscript for details

3. Synthesis and characterization

Figure S1. Sessile drop contact angle analysis. Micrograph of the contact angle between an aqueous Patent Blue V (PBV) drop (16 μM) and a flat glass surface.

Figure S2. Powder X-ray diffraction data. pXRD patterns of CF and both faces of nCF, related to Figure 2, main manuscript. Inset: enlarged pattern between 32 degree and 42 degree.

Figure S3. Fabrication of the POM-IL@nCF composite.

Supplemental explanation related to Figure S3

Step 1: preparation of POM-IL (2.0 g), Step 2: preparation of POM-IL solution in acetone (10 mL), Step 3: **nCF** in a glass container, Step 4: **nCF** immersing in the POM-IL solution, Step 5: deposition process for 24 h in a sealed container, Step 6: solvent removal in air, Step 7: **POM-IL@nCF** obtained after vacuum drying.

Figure S4. SEM images of POM-IL@nCF composite. (a-c) black face, and (d- f) blue face at different magnifications.

Figure S5. SEM images of POM-IL@CF. Micrographs shown at different magnifications.

Figure S6. SEM-EDX mapping of oxygen in POM-IL@nCF. Data corresponds to other SEM-EDX mapping shown in Figure 3a, main manuscript.

Table S2. Textural properties of different materials from N₂ sorption analysis.

Substrate	BET surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)	BJH pore volume (cm ³ g ⁻¹)
CF	5.163	0.007
nCF	7.517	0.015
POM-IL@CF	2.186	0.004
POM-IL@nCF	2.383	0.005

Figure S7. Sessile drop contact angle analysis. Analysis of the contact angle between aqueous PBV solution ($16 \mu\text{M}$) and the sample surface.

Supplemental explanation related to Figure S7b

The PBV drop permeated immediately into the nCF surface.

4. Flow reactor and flow rate calibration

Figure S8. Flow device and internal structure. (a) Set-up for the flow system. (b) Inner structure of the reactor chamber, containing 4 **POM-IL@nCF** composites (with dimensions of 2, 10, and 20 mm corresponding to thickness, width, and length respectively) positioned on a customized holder and (c) flow chart of the reactor chamber.

Supplemental explanation related to Figure S8a

Components description: 1-reservoir, 2-reactor chamber, 3-peristaltic pump, 4-UV-Vis-measuring cell (Outer diameter: 9.85 mm, inner diameter: 7.85 mm, length: 83 mm) with a black cover.

Figure S9. Flow rate calibration before water purification tests. Linear regression to determine a flow rate calibration curve.

5. Studies of organic pollutants removal

Figure S10. PBV removal performance of POM-IL@nCF composite under static (non-flow) conditions. (a) UV-Vis spectra collected at different time and (b) corresponding removal percentages.

Figure S11. PBV removal performance by POM-IL@nCF composite. Supporting data for the information shown in Figure 4a, main manuscript. (a-c) UV-Vis spectra collected at different flow rates as indicated.

Figure S12. PBV removal performance by reference materials. Supporting data related to Figure 4b, main manuscript. UV-Vis spectra collected at flow rate of 125.7 mL min⁻¹ for (a) **POM-IL@CF**, (b) **CF**, and (c) **nCF**.

Figure S13. Reusability of the POM-IL@nCF composite for PBV removal from water under flow. Supporting data related to Figure 4c, main manuscript. UV-Vis spectra collected at flow rate of 125.7 mL min⁻¹ for (a) run 1, (b) run 2, (c) run 3, (d) run 4, (e) run 5, and (f) run 6.

Figure S14. Fitting data from the linear range of removal trends of different runs. Supporting data related to Figure 4c, main manuscript. Slope unit: % min⁻¹.

Table S3. Comparison of PBV removal performance of this work and related studies using polyoxometalate based supported ionic liquid phases, POM-SILPs.

	Reference ⁹	Reference ¹⁰	This work
Filter composite	POM-IL@SiO ₂	POM-IL@Fe ₂ O ₃ @SiO ₂	POM-IL@nCF
Substrate	SiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃ @SiO ₂	nCF
POM-IL loading	21 wt %	20 wt %	71.25 wt %
Dye concentration	32 μM	32 μM	16 μM
Dye volume	10 mL	5 mL	150 mL
Dye amount	320 nmol	160 nmol	2400 nmol
Adsorption time	24 h	24 h	2 h (120 min)
Flow rate	6 mL min ⁻¹	N/A	125.67 mL min⁻¹
Removal percentage	95 %	99 %	ca. 93 %
			2232 nmol (run 1)
			2172 nmol (run 2)
			2094 nmol (run 3)
Dye uptake	304 nmol	158.4 nmol	2049.6 nmol (run 4)
			1528 nmol (run 5)
			1267 nmol (run 6)
Reusability	N/A	N/A	6 runs (720 min)

Figure S15. Reusability of the support material. pXRD patterns of the (a) blue and (b) black face of the fresh nCF and recovered nCF post PBV removal tests. (c) Photographs of the fresh and recovered nCF supports.

Figure S16. Sessile drop contact angle analysis. Sessile drop analysis of the contact angle between an aqueous PBV solution (16 μ M) and the POM-IL@nCF composite surface under different conditions as indicated.

Figure S17. SEM images of POM-IL@nCF surface after PBV removal after different time intervals. (a-c) 52 min, (d-f) run 1 (120 min), (g-i) run 4 (480 min) and (j-l) run 6 (720 min).

Figure S18. PBV removal performance of POM-IL@nCF composite. (a) UV-Vis spectra collected under acidic condition (pH= 3.6) and (b) comparison of the PBV removal trends of POM-IL@nCF at pH 3.6 and pH 6.3 (flow rate: 125.7 mL min⁻¹).

Figure S19. RhB removal performance of POM-IL@nCF. (a) time-lapse UV-Vis spectra (0 min – 600 min) and (b) corresponding removal percentages (flow rate: 125.7 mL min⁻¹).

Figure S20. Mixed PBV and RhB removal performance by POM-IL@nCF composite. (a) UV-Vis spectra collected at different time and (b) corresponding removal percentages (flow rate: 125.7 mL min⁻¹).

6. Supporting References

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